

**INCREASING TRENDS OF NON-PERFORMING ASSETS IN INDIA - ECONOMIC
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ITM Vocational University, Vadodara, Gujrat.**Abstract**

It is well known that level of banks' credit plays an important role in economic developments. Indian banking sector has played a seminal role in supporting economic growth in India. Recently, Indian banks are experiencing consistent increase in non-performing assets (NPA). In this perspective, this paper investigates the trends in NPA in Indian banks and its determinants. The panel regressions, fixed effect allows evaluating the impact of selected macroeconomic variables on the NPA. The Panel regression result indicates that the GDP growth, change in exchange rate and global volatility have major effects on the NPA level of Indian banking sector. This research paper encompasses the magnitude of NPAs and their major causes, in Public Sector Banks in India. The objective of this research paper is to study the trends of NPA, and the loss caused by NPAs to the banking sector, as a whole. The methodology applied for analysis of data is, Percentage method, as the paper relies on secondary data. The findings of the study reveal that the alternative hypothesis is accepted. That is, social factors have significant impact on repayment of loans, by borrowers.

Keywords: NPAs, trends of NPA, social factors, Public Sector Banks**I. INTRODUCTION:-**

Banking system has shown remarkable dynamism and flexibility for adaptation towards adjusting itself to the changes in the economic system. Banking sector in India is no exception to the above phenomena and has undergone major transformation twice, over the last five decades. Firstly, the nationalization of State Bank of India in 1955 followed by the nationalization of 20 leading commercial banks in 2 phases in 1969 and 1984 has brought about a dimensional and directional change in the philosophy and functioning of banking from conventional banking to banking that addresses the needs of the masses. Post nationalisation, the accent was on taking banking extensively to the countryside. As a result, banking in India witnessed an extension of services to rural India as well as to the urban side and also increased disbursement of credit, particularly in priority and preferred sector of the economy and also in the mobilization of deposit. Secondly, the reform initiative started in 1992-93 in the banking industry with the primary motive of making the Indian banking system stable, competitive, transparent, and vibrant which brought a total shift in the mindset of bankers in India from mass banking to prudent banking. In this direction, a series of policy initiatives were introduced as per the recommendations of the Narasimha committee in two phases. Firstly during 1992-93 to 1997-98 (first phase of reforms), the primary objective was to stop erosion in the health of banking, bring uniformity in banking practices, and transparency in the balance sheet of banking companies in India. Until 1992-93, the banks which were a part of a highly regulated system were functionaries in a restricted competitive economy. Both the financial institutions and their products were regulated by the strict legal framework in all aspects

including rates of interest. During these days commercial banks in India were under Government-arranged arrangements with a high segmented market with imperfect antagonism and a few substitute products. The banking industry moved step by step from a regulated frame-work to a deregulated fiscal system. The developments were augmented by liberalization and globalization, which resulted in changes in the intermediation function of Indian Banks. The swiftness of conversion was further considerable with suitable support of technical changes. Finally with the second phase of reform, from 1998-99 onwards, the main focus was shifted towards raising Indian banking to international standards. Accordingly, the financial sector was thrown open for superior global competition under WTO. Banks had to get ready to meet rigorous prudential norms of capital adequacy of BASEL II and also had to deal with challenges thrown up by technical innovations in banking arena. Commercial banks in India accepted the challenges in a befitting manner to suitably adapt to such changes.

II. NPA STATUS ACROSS THE GLOBE AND IN INDIA:-

If we look at from Asian perspective, non-performing assets have become a matter of concern since the Asian crisis in 1997-98 which hit hard the Asian Tigers like Thailand, Indonesia, Malaysia and also China. India was not hit such badly by the crisis. Before the crisis commercial banks in those countries were very poorly capitalized and running high level of non-performing assets. The main indicator, Gross NPA as percentage of total loans reached 48.6 per cent in Indonesia, 42.9 per cent in Thailand, 18.6 per cent in Malaysia during 1998. It reached to a maximum of 29.8 per cent in China in 2001. Indian banking sector performed much better during this time with Gross NPA to total loan ratio of only 14.4 per cent in 1998. But as we can see ratio of non-performing loans to total loans has fallen sharply in Asian countries, signaling the recovery of the banking sector. That happened because of the several measures taken by the respective countries. Prior to the 1997-98 financial crises, Asian banks were exposed to very large credit risks; badly managed and poorly supervised, apart from being inadequately capitalized for the risks. Several complex forces and macroeconomic factors acted together to change financial intermediation in Asia since the 1997-98 crisis. One factor is the sharp rise in aggregate savings in the Asian countries. Another is substantial accumulation of foreign exchange reserves led to a major rise in central bank or government paper held by the banks, providing them with low-risk and very liquid assets. Some of the earlier inefficiencies have disappeared and lending functions of the banks have changed considerably in the past decade. Substantial consolidation took place between 1999 and 2004, which has also increased competition and efficiency of the Asian banking system. Many countries closed their weaker banks or merged their banking institutions (varying between 10 to 30 percent of total banks in India, Indonesia, Korea and Malaysia) or privatized them (Mohanty and Turner, 2010). The credit deployment by the banking system in the economy has a direct impact on the non-performing loan level of the country. Credit is required for faster growth of the economy but any kind of macroeconomic shock can impact those outstanding advances badly and may turn them non-performing.

During the 1997-98 Asian financial crises Indian banks were in much better position than its Asian peers in the matter of non-performing assets. The globalization effect was less in India and Indian economy was more decoupled than countries like Thailand, Malaysia, and Indonesia which were directly controlled by the capital flows from the west. So, Indian banks were less vulnerable to global shocks. The Gross NPA as percentage of total loans was at 14.4 per cent, much lower than the Asian peers. The NPA levels then improved over the next decade and marginally deteriorated during the next global crisis of 2008. However, in 2011-12 the NPA ratios deteriorated further. This may be the

impact of excess lending during the crisis period to keep the economy moving and the growth intact. Now if we look at the NPA levels of different bank groups, historically foreign banks had the least level of NPA. The other bank groups had much higher level of NPA at the beginning of the last decade. While both old and new private sector banks were able to reduce their NPA level at a very comfortable level, public sector banks were unable to do so. In 2011-12 the NPA ratio of old private sector banks, new private sector banks and foreign banks were almost similar but that of public sector banks were much higher. The highest NPA ratio was for the State Bank of India Group which includes country's largest lender State Bank of India. There are many studies regarding NPA in India including Ranjan and Dhal (2003), Yadav (2011), Ghosh and Ghosh (2011), Roy and Bhattacharya (2011) etc. But most of them focused only on public sector banks. But now the private sector banks also have grown substantially. So, there is a need for a study to analyze the NPA taking the whole banking sector in India into account. The study by Reserve Bank of India's Ranjan and Dhal (2003) was one of the landmark studies of the NPA of Indian banks after the Asian financial crisis. They did an empirical assessment of relation between non-performing assets and terms of credit of public sector banks using linear regression model. In favorable macroeconomic conditions the chances of defaulting decreases as the borrower wants to maintain his credit worthiness. The study also identified Pro-cyclical behavior of lending of the banks observed in other countries like China. Banks tend to lend more during economic expansion period due to amplification of asymmetric information and moral hazard. This in turn caused more defaults.

The lending policy of the banks is one of the causes for NPAs as pointed out by many researchers not only for India but for other countries also. Deterioration of the quality of advances in Indian public sector banks over the years can be attributed to aggressive lending policies undertaken by the banks (Ghosh and Ghosh, 2011). The same pro-cyclic lending behavior of banks discussed by Reddy (2004), Ranjan and Dhal (2003) and several others combined with poor lending policies caused the banks to lend more in pre-recession period i.e., before FY 2008-09. That resulted in the increase in the NPA level in the subsequent years. Inability of the banks to monitor and control the NPAs in the post-recession years proves the absence of proper pre-sanctioning appraisal and post-disbursement control within the public sector banks in India (Ghosh and Ghosh, 2011).

Now to find out the impact of macroeconomic factors on non-performing assets in Indian banks, there are very few studies. Das and Ghosh (2003) empirically examined non-performing loans of public sector banks of India in terms of macroeconomic condition along with various indicators like asset size, credit growth and operating efficiency indicators. In the macroeconomic stress testing of public sector banks factors such as output gap, Real Effective Exchange Rate appreciation above its trend value, inflation rate and monetary tightening i.e., rise in interest rate significantly affect banks' asset quality as found out empirically by Roy and Bhattacharya (2011). The study found that the coefficient for output gap and inflation rate have positive signs while the coefficient of REER deviation from trend is negative. The NPA level measured by default rate responds positively to inflationary shocks and also to the volatility of exchange rate (Roy and Bhattacharya, 2011).

Higher NPA levels of banks in the last decade prompted several actions from the Government of India and Reserve Bank of India in form of policy measures in the areas of debt recovery, securitization and asset reconstruction, resolution of defaults and non-performing assets (Ranjan and Dhal, 2003). Narasimhan committee was set up in 1991 to provide a road map for the banking sector reforms and to build a robust banking system in the country. The committee suggested that Indian banks should follow the international practice in defining a NPA (Jain, 2012). The committee also advocated for a proper system of income recognition and provisioning which is fundamental for the

preservation of the strength and stability of the banking system. Another big step was The Securitization and Reconstruction of Financial Assets and Enforcement of Security Interest (SARFAESI) Act, 2002, which was passed on December 17, 2002. Along with this Debt Recovery Tribunals (DRTs) and Lok Adalat's were also formed for recovering NPAs. A more systematic surveillance and more internal review of health of loan accounts at a quicker pace when they are still in standard category can help prevent slippage of assets to a large extent (Rao, 2012).

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. Analysis of defaulting borrower's perceptions that are responsible for NPAs in the target bank and area
2. To evolve suggestive measures to minimize NPA incidence.

IV. HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

The hypothesis of this study is as follows:

- (i) Socio-economic factors impacting the loan repayments by Customers

V. ANALYSIS

Trends in NPAs of Total Scheduled Commercial Banks (SCBs). Non-Performing Assets percentage in India from 2013 to 2019 is as follows

Table – 1: Trends of NPA in Indian Banks

Years	NPA % in India
2013	2.7%
2014	3.4%
2015	4%
2016	4.3%
2017	5.10%
2018	9.1%
2019	8.9%
2020	9.6%

**TABLE 2: Net NPA to Net Advances of Scheduled Commercial Banks in India
(Rs. in crores)**

Years	Net Advances	Net NPA Amount
2013	75000	2896400000
2014	100000	3268400000
2015	125000	3298700000
2016	150000	3468500000
2017	175000	3654700000
2018	200000	4205100000

2019	225000	4358200000
2020	2694000	5258710000

Trends in NPAs of Public Sector Banks:

Indian Public Sector Banks have been perceived as the vehicles of social change and also played a pivotal role in stepping up credit for agricultural and rural development. Banks have also been shouldering the responsibility of social banking for a variety of poverty alleviation or self-employment programmes. This has to be kept in view while analysing the level of Non-Performing Assets in banks. The gross and net NPAs of Public Sector Banks vis-à-vis the gross and net advances of the Banks in general and the growth scenario have been presented in Table.2. It can be viewed from the table that the gross advances of Rs.2,84,971 Crores in 1998 have increased to Rs.14,64,493 Crores by the year 2002 with a growth rate of 19.9 percent. Contrarily the amount of gross NPAs of the order of Rs.45,653 Crores in 1998 declined to stand at Rs.38,968 Crores registering a negative growth rate of 1.7 percent. The decline in the absolute amount of gross NPAs of the Public Sector Banks is evident since 2002 where it is Rs.56,473 Crores. A further analysis reveals that, over the years under review, the annual rate of growth in gross NPAs experienced a marked decline from 13.2 per cent to stand at -14.80 per cent in 2006 and -5.77 per cent in 2007. It can also be visualised from the data that the net advances of public sector banks recorded a growth rate of 24.1 per cent increasing from Rs.2,06,459 Crores in 1998 to Rs.14,40,123 Crores in 2007. As against this, the net NPAs which were Rs.21,232 Crores in 1998, though went upto Rs.27,969 Crores (2001) however consistently declined to Rs.15,145 Crores with a growth rate of -3.7 per cent. It is also clear from the fact that the annual rate of growth in net NPAs of public sector banks which was 14.03 per cent in 1999 gradually have come down registering a negative growth rate of -16.72 per cent in 2006 and only 3.95 per cent in 2007. The analysis helps to observe that in the case of public sector banks, the NPAs have remarkably come down in spite of the impressive growth in advances.

Public Sector Banks – Loan Asset Classification:

The loan asset classification of Public Sector Banks during 1993-2007 is presented in Table 2 to focus on the anatomy of NPAs. As evident from the table, which also reflects the proportion of NPAs to total advances over the years, the proportion of total NPAs to total advances in PSBs was 23.2 per cent in 1993 and marginally increased to 24.8 per cent in 1994, wherein an incessant decline had been experienced to stand at 2.7 per cent by 2007. Moreover, out of the total advances of the PSBs, the component of Standard Assets which was 76.5 per cent in 1993, though dropped down marginally to 75.02 per cent in 1994, continuously looked up to record appreciably at 97.3 per cent by 2007. On the other hand, the proportion of loss assets to total advances which was 2.3 per cent and 2.4 per cent respectively in 1993 and 1994 dived to the ground to stand at 0.3 per cent in 2007. Most positively the sub-standard assets and also the doubtful assets followed suit. In addition, it could be further noted that the total advances and standard assets of the PSBs registered an appreciable growth rate of 27.1 per cent and 30.5 per cent respectively over the years. But the total NPAs, doubtful assets, loss assets and substandard assets registered a negative or negligible growth during the period under review. The analysis thus reveals that, though the Net advances of the Public Sector Banks experienced a galloping increase over the years, the loss assets, the total NPAs have been well bridled and the standard assets well improved.

The GNPA ratio of all SCBs declined in 2018-19 after rising for seven consecutive years, as recognition of bad loans neared completion. Decline in the slippage ratio¹⁰ as well as a reduction in outstanding

GNPAs helped in improving the GNPA ratio. While a part of the write-offs was due to ageing of the loans, recovery efforts received a boost from the IBC. The restructured standard advances to gross advances ratio began declining after the asset quality review (AQR) in 2015 and reached 0.55 per cent at end-March 2019 (Chart IV.14 b). IV.30 All bank groups recorded an improvement in asset quality, with PSBs experiencing a drop both in the GNPA and in the net NPA ratios (Table IV.8). The deteriorating asset quality of PVBs in terms of the GNPA ratio is due to the reclassification of IDBI Bank Ltd as a private bank effective January 21, 2019; however, after excluding IDBI Bank Ltd, PVBs' GNPA ratio declined. Supervisory data suggest that the GNPA ratio of SCBs remained stable at 9.1 per cent at end-September 2019. IV.31 Consistent with these developments, the proportion of standard assets in total advances of SCBs increased in 2018-19, largely because of the improved performance of PSBs. The corresponding improvement in sub-standard and doubtful assets was partly reversed by an increase in the loss account (Table IV.9). Chart IV.14: Asset Quality of Banks Note: GNPA ratio is calculated using annual accounts of banks and off-site returns (global operations). Source: Annual accounts of banks and Off-site returns. a. GNPA Ratio Per cent b. Restructured Standard Advances to Gross Advances Per cent c. GNPA Write-offs GNPA write-offs at the end of the year as per cent of GNPAs at the beginning of the Year Reduction in GNPAs at the end of the year as per cent of GNPAs at the beginning of the Year d. Reduction in GNPAs All SCBs PSBs PVBs FBs All SCBs PSBs PVBs FBs All SCBs PSBs PVBs FBs All SCBs

Time gap between applying and sanctioning of loan:

Time lag is a factor, which plays a crucial role with respect to the respondent's interest, miscellaneous expenditure, business activities and above all, the customer service. The main reason of the lag in sanctioning loan is security problem. If the gap is more, it creates more financial problems to the borrowers.

An analysis of the Table-VI.2 shows the time gap between applying for loan and sanctioning of the loan. Out of 223 respondents, a majority of 114 (51.1%) revealed that there is a gap of 2 months and another 53 (23.8%) felt that there is one month gap, whereas. About 23 (10.3%) respondents expressed in anguish that there is a gap of 6months. In addition to 0.4 per cent of the respondents reported that the time gap is surprisingly 12 months. Thus, it comes to light that the average time gap between applying for loan and sanctioning of loan is two and half months. It is further observed that 80.3 per cent of the loans were sanctioned within 2 months from the time of applying or even less than that.

Table-3: time gap between applying for the loan and sanctionof the loan

Sl. No.	Gap in Months	Number	Percentage	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percentage
1	1	53	23.8	23.8	23.8
2	2	114	51.1	51.1	74.9
3	3	12	5.4	5.4	80.3
4	4	12	5.4	5.4	85.7
5	5	3.1	3.1	3.1	88.8
6	6	23	10.3	10.3	99.1
Total		223	100	100	

Source: Survey.

Time gap between sanction and disbursement of the Loan:

An attempt is also made to know the gap between sanctioning of loan and receiving loan. As presented in Table-VI.3, out of the 223 respondents, a majority of 174(78.0%) expressed that the time gap between sanctioning of loan and receipt of loan is one month and another 48 (21.5%) felt that they received the loan 2 months after sanctioning. Thus, the average time gap between sanctioning of the loan and receiving loan is 1.2 months.

Table-4: gap between sanction and disbursement of the loan

Sl. No.	Gap in Months	Number	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
1	1	174	78	78
2	1.5	1	0.5	78.5
3	2	48	21.5	100.0
Total		223	100	

Source: Survey.

Time gap between receiving and utilisation of loan by the unit

Table 4 presents the revelation of the respondents regarding the time gap between receiving and utilisation of loan by the unit. An analysis of data shows that out of 223 respondents, a majority of 123 (55.2%) stated that they utilised the received loan within one month followed by 35.9 per cent who revealed that they utilised the loan amount after 3 months. On the whole, 91.5 per cent of the respondents are observed to have utilised the loan amount for the unit within 2 months or less than 2 months. The average time gap between receiving the loan and utilisation of loan by the unit is observed to be 1.54 months.

Table – 5: Financial Performance/Results of Selected banks

Net Profit (Rupees in corer)							
Year	SBI	BOI	UBI	BOB	IOB	PNB	CBI
2011	4541.31	1125.95	267.28	1026.46	1008.43	1540.08	498.01
2012	6729.12	1960.28	318.95	1435.52	1202.34	2048.76	550.16
2013	9121.23	3009.41	184.71	2227.20	1325.79	3090.88	571.24
2014	9166.05	1738.56	322.96	3058.33	706.96	3905.36	1058.23
2015	7370.35	2488.71	523.97	4241.68	1072.54	4433.50	1252.41
2016	11707.29	2674.62	632.53	5006.96	1050.13	4884.20	533.04
2017	14104.98	2741.91	391.90	4480.72	567.23	4747.67	1014.96
2018	10891.17	2732.65	-1213.44	4541.08	601.74	3342.58	-1262.84
2019	13101.57	1748.32	255.99	3398.44	-454.33	3061.58	606.45
2020	9950.65	-6334.98	-281.96	-5395.54	-2897.33	3944.40	-1117.67

This is the trend of Net Profit for the different banks for the years 2011 –2020. Almost all the banks have experienced a negative growth in the year 2018. A remarkable difference in the financial status of the banks was observed in the year 2018. All the banks except SBI and PNB went through a severe loss

in the year. The loss percent of the banks- BOI, BOB, IOB, CBI and UBI in the year 2018 as compared to 2017 were 462.32, 258.77, 537.71, 284.30, and 210.14 respectively. Among the banks, only SBI and PNB could achieve profit consistently in all the years.

Table –6: Gross NPA's of Selected banks

Gross NPA (Rupees in corer)							
Year	SBI	BOI	UBI	BOB	IOB	PNB	CBI
2011	9998.00	0.00	744.30	0.00	1120.00	3390.72	2572.00
2012	12837.34	0.00	817.00	2400.69	997.00	3319.30	2350.00
2013	15588.6	0.00	761.00	1842.92	1923.40	2767.46	2316.50
2014	19534.89	0.00	1019.60	1981.38	3611.00	3214.41	2457.90
2015	25326.29	4811.55	1355.78	3152.50	3089.00	4379.39	2394.53
2016	39676.46	5893.97	2176.42	4464.75	3920.00	8719.62	7273.46
2017	51189.39	8765.25	2963.83	7982.58	6607.00	13465.79	8456.18
2018	61605.35	11868.80	7118.01	11875.90	9020.00	18880.06	11500.01
2019	56725.34	22193.24	6552.91	16261.45	14922.00	25694.86	11873.06
2020	98172.80	49879.12	9471.01	40521.04	30048.00	55818.33	22720.88

The gross NPA have been continuously increasing for all he banks for he specified period. As the business operations of the bank increasing the amount of NPAs have also increased. NPA of the banks went on increasing in all the years but a drastic raise was observed in the year 2018. The percentage raise of NPA of the banks in the year 2016 as compared to 2017 were SBI – 73.07, BOI- 124.75, UBI- 44.53, BOB- 149.18, IOB-101.37, PNB- 117 and CBI- 91.36

Table –7: Correlation between NPA and Net Profit of the selected banks

Bank	Correlation
State Bank of India	0.591125611
Bank of India	-0.863792026
United Bank of India	-0.654074198
Bank of Baroda	-0.720973007
Indian Overseas Bank	-0.985503809
Panjab National Bank	0.194168193
Central Bank India	-0.73857971

It is very clear that correlation for SBI and PNB are equal to 0.591 and 0.194 respectively. It means that there is a positive relation between Net Profits and NPA. It means that as profits increase NPA also increase. NPA is directly related to Total Advances given by bank and banks main source of income is interest earned by bank. But other banks are negative correlation. NPAs are increasing in every year but net profit decrease. The data for NPA and the bank level variables are obtained from various issues of Report on Trend and Progress of Banking in India published by Reserve Bank of India. The data for macroeconomic variables are collected from various issues of Handbook of Statistics on Indian Economy published by the central bank. Many variables were considered while estimation. But only the significant variables are included in the baseline specification. Initially we considered total 12

variables of which four are bank specific variables eight are economic variables. But to be considered in the regression analysis the variables must be stationary in nature. So, after discarding the non-stationary variables we ultimately kept five variables for the regression analysis (Table 8). Among them one is bank level variable and rest four are macroeconomic variables. The bank level variable is the Net Interest Margin (NIM). The Macroeconomic variables are GDP growth rate (GDP), change in Real Effective Exchange Rate (REER), Inflation measured by Wholesale Price Index (WPI). Also, to take in account the effect of the external sector the “Global Variable”, change in CBOE Volatility Index (VIX), based on S&P 500 Index Options is included. The Panel Unit Root Test (ADF - Fisher Chi-square) result for the variables is given in Table 8. Overall, the data includes 85 observations evenly distributed over five cross sections i.e., bank segments.

Table-8: Panel Unit Root Test (ADF - Fisher Chi-Square) Result

Sl. No.	Variable	Statistic	Probability
1	NET PROFIT	12.7590	0.2375
2	NIM	19.8681	0.0305
3	PROVISION	14.1047	0.1683
4	OPERATING EXPENSES	10.0374	0.4372
5	GDP	24.7000	0.0059
6	PER CAPITA GNP	8.21741	0.6076
7	BROAD MONEY	11.0703	0.3521
8	DEBT GDP	5.41440	0.8618
9	INTEREST RATE	3.76614	0.9573
10	REER	58.2100	0.0000
11	WPI	27.8891	0.0019
12	VIX	26.8455	0.0028

Panel Regression Model of the form-

$$Y_t = \alpha B_t + \beta M_t + \gamma G_t + \varepsilon$$

Here the dependent variable is Net NPA to Net Advances ratio (NPA_ADVANCES). The independent variables are - bank variable NIM shown by B_t , Macroeconomic variables GDP, REER and WPI denoted by M_t and the global variable VIX denoted by G_t . One time period lag of all the independent variables NIM, GDP, REER, WPI and VIX are also included as independent variables. We have used the fixed effect model as estimation technique.

The panel regression result is depicted in the Table 9. From the result we can see that at 95 per cent confidence level the following variables have significant (Prob.<0.05) impacts – both GDP growth rate for current period and with one period lag, Change in Real Effective Exchange Rate (REER), Change in Real Effective Exchange Rate (REER) and change in CBOE Volatility Index (VIX).

The values of R² and Adjusted R² are 65.48 per cent and 57.68 per cent respectively, which implies that the chosen independent variables are explaining the dependent variable to a good extent. Now to analyze and validate the result we need to focus more on the sign of the coefficient than the value. For GDP and its one period lag the signs are negative in both cases. This implies that with decrease in economic growth the NPA level increases. It is quite evident from the current economic data of India; the GDP growth rate slumped to the decade low of about 4 per cent and the NPA level increased to almost 2005 level. The second significant variable is the change in Real Effective Interest Rate. We

need to look how the exchange rate the non-performing asset level of banks economically, it is not as straight forward as the relation between GDP and NPA. The coefficient in REER is having negative sign denoting inverse relationship with non-performing asset level. That means a currency appreciation leads to more NPA. One explanation for that could be the fact that strong currency makes the country's products and services less competitive and thereby decreasing the amount of export. The next variable impacting the level of NPA is the global variable CBOE Volatility Index commonly referred as VIX. This index measures the volatility in the global market. The sign of the coefficient should be positive implying a rise in volatility would also increase the NPA of the banks. But here we get the negative sign which is quite significant. It implies that though the volatility is increasing globally Indian banks are being able to keep the non-performing asset level at a declining trajectory.

Table-9: Panel Regression Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob
NIM	0.597294	0.909739	0.656555	0.5139
NIM (1)	0.620725	0.938126	0.661665	0.5106
GDP	- 0.489214	0.162067	-3.018584	0.0037
GDP (1)	- 0.639092	0.161162	-3.965533	0.0002
WPI	- 0.262397	0.147713	-1.776392	0.0806
WPI (1)	0.063471	0.214663	0.295677	0.7685
VIX	- 0.063884	0.013892	-4.598526	0.0000
VIX (1)	0.019459	0.012080	1.610831	0.1123
REER	- 0.409663	0.111450	-3.675757	0.0005
REER (1)	- 0.125592	0.073609	-1.706196	0.0930
C	8.997514	1.964238	4.580663	0.0000
	R-squared		0.65480	
	Adjusted R-squared		5	
	S.E. of regression		0.57685	
	Sum squared resid		8	
	F-statistic		1.73781	
	Prob(F-statistic)		1	
			187.239	
			1	
			8.40061	
			0	
			0.00000	
			0	

Notes: Method: Panel Least Squares, Periods included: 16, Cross-sections included: 5.95% Confidence
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Level

VI. FINDINGS:-

The analysis brings forth that the gross NPAs of Public Sector Banks declined at a compound rate of -0.5 per cent. The rate of decline is comparatively sharper in the case of net NPAs which declined from Rs.17,567 Crores in 1995 to Rs.15,145 Crores in 2007 registering a rate of decline at 1.13 per cent. The gross NPAs as a ratio of gross advances and total assets which were 23.2 per cent and 11.8 per cent in 1999 respectively, remarkably dropped down to 2.7 per cent and 1.6 per cent respectively in the year 2007. The scenario is similar in the case of net NPAs as a percentage of net advances and also to total assets.

These two ratios which were respectively at 10.7 per cent and 4 per cent in 1995 experienced a marked decline to 1.1 per cent and 0.6 per cent respectively in the year 2007. Thus, it can be concluded that the incidence and intensity of the gross and net NPAs of public sector banks in the post reform period ending with 2007 has diluted over the years as can be observed from the rolling down ratios of gross NPAs and Net NPAs to advances and total assets.

It can be observed from the analysis that among the various parameters and reflections from bankers and borrowers there are quite contradictory views among all the respondents. This is not unusual because the bankers and borrowers cannot have the same opinion about the reasons.

What is true for the bankers may not hold true with the borrower. It is inferred from the analysis that compared to the private sector banks and foreign banks in India, the public sector banks and State Bank group could well contain the proportion of gross NPAs to gross advances. It can be observed that in the case of Nationalised banks the ratio witnessed a decline to 0.9 per cent during 2018-19.

Thus, in the case of all the bank groups especially with respect to the public sector banks the net NPAs as a percentage of Net advances remarkably came down. This indicates the improved recovery performance and a sensibly cautious management of NPAs.

It can be noted that the public sector banks including the nationalised banks Andhra Bank experienced a consistent decline in the ratio of gross NPAs to total assets. The public sector banks which stood with only 1.6 per cent in 2018-19.

The public sector banks including the nationalised banks and State Bank group experienced containment in the problem and incidence of NPAs and stood relatively ahead of the private sector banks and foreign banks in India in controlling the non-performing assets. The analysis reveals that the total advances of AB in the district was Rs.25,578.36 lakhs in 2013 and it increased to Rs.1,76,182.92 lakhs by the year 2018 registering a growth rate of 23.9 per cent.

The gross NPAs and net NPAs respectively stood at Rs.3,527.25 lakhs and Rs.1,729.09 lakhs in 2013 constituting 13.79 per cent and 6.79 per cent respectively of the total advances. By the year 2016, the gross NPAs and Net NPAs of the AB in the district respectively went-up to stand at Rs.6,712.56 lakhs and Rs.3,413.94 lakhs.

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